

THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL DIAGNOSTIC METHODS IN PRACTICE

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Abstract. *This problem can be solved only by students who have studied the discipline “Psychological and Pedagogical Diagnostics”. Psychological and pedagogical diagnostics, being one of the most important disciplines directly related to the practical activities of a vocational teacher, has recently received wide recognition. It acts as one of the ways to apply psychological knowledge in real life situations and occupies an important place in many areas of practical activity that need to take into account the psychological characteristics of a person. For effective assimilation of the presented material, activation of independent cognitive activity of students, development of their ability to link theory with practice, increasing interest and accessibility of the learning process, as well as for the purpose of developing the skills of psychological and pedagogical culture, the manual contains applications, including.*

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One of the main areas where psychodiagnostics is used is the sphere of education and upbringing. Psychological diagnostics acts as a mandatory stage and a means of solving many practical problems that arise in educational institutions. Among them, the following tasks stand out: ● monitoring the intellectual and personal development of students; ● assessment of school maturity; ● identifying the causes of academic failure; ● selection for schools and classes with in-depth study of certain subjects (specialized training); ● solving the problem of students with abnormal, deviant behavior, conflict, aggressive, etc.; ● identification of gifted children; ● vocational guidance, etc. Thus, both psychodiagnostics and pedagogical diagnostics can be considered as the basis of psychological and pedagogical diagnostics.

Diagnostic approaches developed in psychology and pedagogy find their application in psychological and pedagogical diagnostics. However, there is an opinion that the term “psychological-pedagogical diagnostics” is incorrectly used instead of the terms “pedagogical diagnostics” and “psychodiagnostics” without taking into account the dominant focus of diagnostic activity on solving pedagogical or psychological problems. There are a number of differences between pedagogical diagnostics and psychodiagnostics. Pedagogical diagnostics has never been just a “performer” who examines clients on request, notes their signs and then transfers the obtained data to the customer. Pedagogical diagnostics can only perform a service function within the system of education and training.

What is characteristic of pedagogy is not that it is in charge of the process of cognition in a certain area, but that it is the theoretical foundation of practical activity. Pedagogical diagnostics is also subject to the same task. Psychologists have managed to introduce many of their own problems into the discussion around pedagogical diagnostics, although these problems are not relevant to it. Pedagogical diagnostics must be subordinated to pedagogy, and it is necessary to again clearly define its independence in relation to psychodiagnostics. Thanks to psychological

and pedagogical diagnostics, the initial, current and final level of development of personality traits in the educational process is monitored. Based on the results of the initial diagnostic data, a conclusion is made about the sufficient or insufficient development of a particular quality, and on this basis a decision is made on the need for its development or correction. Spending time and effort on developing or correcting this quality only makes sense if its expression is insufficient for the successful implementation of educational and/or professional activities.

Monitoring the current level of development of professionally important qualities and psychological properties is necessary to provide prompt feedback in the processes of training, education and development. Such monitoring makes it possible to make timely adjustments to the management of these processes. Without it, the educational process would be like trying to drive a car blindly when it is impossible to see the road and surroundings. In the social sciences, it is customary to distinguish several methodological approaches to diagnostics, which can also be attributed to psychological and pedagogical diagnostics.

The systematic approach is associated with the determination of the psychological characteristics of the subject, providing the most complete and holistic description of the personality. The normative approach is the determination of deviations of the psychological characteristics of the subject from normative (reference) indicators. The situational approach is the identification of the psychological characteristics of the subject, manifested in certain life situations. The problem approach is the determination of the psychological characteristics of the subject that contribute to the emergence of personal or interpersonal problem situations. Each approach has its own advantages and limitations. Often these approaches complement each other.

The research model of psychological and pedagogical diagnostics includes the following components: 1. Conceptual model of the diagnostic process and object. 2. A set of diagnostic techniques. 3. Diagnostic process. 4. Making a diagnosis. A conceptual model is necessary to determine the direction of diagnostic activity, since in commercial structures, the army, internal affairs bodies, industrial production, recruiting agencies, etc. In each of these areas there are specific conditions for the use of psychodiagnostic tools, specific psychodiagnostic tasks and methods that make up the subject private or special psychodiagnostics (professional, sports, clinical, etc.). In various spheres of life and types of activity, practical problems arise, the success of which depends on taking into account the individual or group psychological characteristics of people.

Thus, in the practice of education and upbringing it is necessary to identify psychological differences between children in order to implement an individual approach to them. To ensure effective professional activity, selection based on psychological and psychophysiological qualities is sometimes required. A psychological diagnosis can be the basis for optimal professional self-determination of an individual. Creating a normal socio-psychological climate in a work team is often impossible without analyzing business and personal qualities. The number of examples of practical problems requiring a psychological diagnosis can be increased many times over. Psychological diagnostics is a component of the professional activity of any psychologist, psychologist-teacher, psychologist-consultant, psychotherapist, psychologist-trainer, etc. Whatever the psychologist does - individual counseling, vocational guidance, psychotherapy, whatever field he works in - the basis his activity is psychological diagnostics.

In scientific and practical psychodiagnostics, a number of typical tasks have been identified. These include: 1. Determining whether a person has one or another psychological

property or behavioral characteristic. 2. Determination of the degree of development of a given property, its expression in specific quantitative and qualitative indicators. 3. Description of the diagnosable psychological and behavioral characteristics of a person in cases where this is necessary. 4. Comparison of the degree of development of the studied properties in different people includes significant psychological characteristics of the subject and their significant connections. The use of a conceptual model is possible after operationalization: it is necessary to formulate empirical indicators, parameters that can be measured. It is empirical indicators that will be used in diagnosing the psychological state of the subject and interpreting the data obtained. The term “psychodiagnostics,” which spread in psychiatry after the appearance of G. Rorschach’s book “Psychodiagnostics” in 1921, quickly went beyond the boundaries of medicine.

In defining the concept of psychodiagnostics, attention is drawn to the duality of the approach to the definition of the term “psychodiagnostics” 2. One of the definitions of psychodiagnostics, according to R. S. Nemov, refers it to a special area of psychological knowledge concerning the development and use in practice of various psychodiagnostic tools. Another definition of the term “psychodiagnostics” indicates the specifics of the psychologist’s activities related to the practical formulation of a psychological diagnosis. Also, two sides of psychodiagnostics are reflected in the works of other authors. Thus, M.K. Akimova identifies two functions of psychodiagnostics - scientific (as a research area for the design of psychodiagnostic methods) and practical (the use of psychodiagnostic methods). Of course, this division of psychodiagnostics is conditional, since these two characteristics are found in the activities of the same the same specialists.

Thus, the creators of psychodiagnostic methods not only test them in practice, but also solve certain practical problems that arise in the work of practical psychologists. Psychodiagnostic research (more precisely, examination) has an important characteristic that distinguishes it from scientific research. A research psychologist (including a researcher in the field of psychodiagnostics) is focused on searching for unknown patterns connecting abstract variables, uses “known” (i.e., defined by some characteristic) subjects and neglects their individual differences and empirical integrity. For the practicing psychodiagnostician, it is these individual differences and empirical integrity that are the object of study; it is focused on searching for known patterns in “unknown” subjects³. Currently, practical psychodiagnostics finds its application in various fields and activities, where the success of solving problems depends on taking into account the individual or group psychological characteristics of people. Essentially, taking into account the individual psychological characteristics of people is necessary to increase efficiency in any activity.

Psychodiagnostic methods and procedures are especially widely used in such areas as education, medicine, and sports; All four listed tasks in practical psychodiagnostics are solved individually or comprehensively, depending on the goals of the examination. Moreover, in almost all cases, with the exception of a qualitative description of the results, proficiency in methods of quantitative analysis, in particular mathematical statistics, is required. General psychodiagnostics is to a certain extent abstracted from specific diagnostic tasks that arise in various particular areas of psychodiagnostics. However, a psychodiagnostician must be aware of these tasks, since they largely determine the limitations in the use of methods. One of the important differences applies not only to tasks, but also to psychodiagnostic situations in general. This is the distinction between the client situation and the examination situation.

In the first situation, a person turns to a psychologist for help, he willingly cooperates, tries to follow the instructions as accurately as possible, and has no conscious intentions to embellish himself or falsify the results. In the second situation, a person knows that he is being examined, tries to “pass the exam,” and to do this, he quite consciously controls his behavior and his answers so as to appear in the most advantageous light (or achieve his goal even at the cost of simulating deviations and disorders). In a client situation, much less stringent requirements can be placed on a diagnostic tool regarding its protection from falsification due to a conscious strategy than in an examination situation. Psychodiagnostic tasks (and psychodiagnostic situations in general) can also be distinguished from the point of view of who will use diagnostic data and how and what is the responsibility of the psychodiagnostician for choosing ways to intervene in the situation of the subject. Let us briefly describe these situations.

The data is used by a related specialist to make a non-psychological diagnosis or formulate an administrative decision. This situation is typical for the use of psychodiagnostic data in medicine. The psychologist makes a judgment about the specific characteristics of thinking, memory, and personality of the patient, and the doctor makes a medical diagnosis. The psychologist is not responsible either for the diagnosis or for what kind of treatment the doctor will provide to the patient. The same scheme applies to the use of psychodiagnostic data in psychodiagnostics at the request of the court, a comprehensive psychological and psychiatric examination, psychodiagnostics of the professional competence of an employee or professional suitability at the request of the administration. 2. The data is used by the psychodiagnostician himself to make a psychological diagnosis, although intervention in the situation of the subject is carried out by a specialist of a different profile. This is, for example, the situation of psychodiagnostics in relation to the search for the causes of school failure: the diagnosis is psychological (or psychological-pedagogical) in nature, and the work to implement it is carried out by teachers, parents, and other educators. 3. The data is used by the psychodiagnostician himself to make a psychological diagnosis, and the latter serves as the basis for him (or the basis for the actions of his fellow psychologist) for developing ways of psychological influence. This is the situation of psychodiagnostics in the conditions of psychological consultation. 4. Diagnostic data is used by the examinee himself for the purposes of self-development, behavior correction, etc. In this situation, the psychologist is responsible for the correctness of the data, for the ethical, deontological aspects of the diagnosis and only partially for how this diagnosis will be used by the client. Thus, psychodiagnostics as an established scientific and practical activity is the methodological basis of psychological and pedagogical diagnostics.

Due to the fact that the status of pedagogical diagnostics is still not defined, there are different definitions of this concept. Some authors identify pedagogical diagnostics with control and verification of learning results (V.V. Voronov, etc.), others associate pedagogical diagnostics only with control methods (V.I. Kagan, N.A. Sychenikov, etc.), others reveal the essence pedagogical diagnostics through a description of a set of activities². Thus, according to the definition of K. Ingenkamp, “pedagogical diagnostics is designed, firstly, to optimize the process of individual learning, secondly, in the interests of society, to ensure the correct definition of learning outcomes and, thirdly, guided by the developed criteria, to minimize errors in translation students from one study group to another, when sending them to various courses and choosing a specialization of study”³. There is a fourth approach to the definition of the concept of “pedagogical diagnostics”: the content of the concept includes control, verification, evaluation,

accumulation of statistical data, their analysis, identification of dynamics, trends, and forecasting of further developments⁴. According to K. Ingenkamp, pedagogical diagnostics can be considered in a narrow and broad sense. In a narrow sense, diagnostics is a subject whose content consists of planning and control of the educational process and the process of cognition.

Here, pedagogical diagnostics is a means of establishing a connection between academic performance and prerequisites for learning, assessing the correctness of the choice of educational goals based on certain conditions in which the educational process takes place. In a broad sense, it covers all diagnostic tasks within educational counseling. Pedagogical diagnostics in this case acts as a means of tracking and optimizing the development process of subjects of the educational process¹. In the concept of “pedagogical diagnostics,” the adjective “pedagogical” characterizes the following features of this diagnostic: • firstly, diagnostics is carried out for pedagogical purposes, that is, it is aimed at obtaining new information on how to improve the quality of education (training, upbringing) and development of the student’s personality; • secondly (and this is the main thing), it provides fundamentally new meaningful information about the quality of the teacher’s pedagogical work; • thirdly, it is carried out using methods that organically fit into the logic of the teacher’s pedagogical activity; • fourthly, with the help of pedagogical diagnostics, the control and evaluation functions of the teacher’s activities are strengthened; • fifthly, even some traditionally used means and methods of teaching and upbringing can be transformed into means and methods of pedagogical diagnostics². In professional pedagogy, pedagogical diagnostics is considered as a special type of activity, which is the establishment and study of signs characterizing the state and results of the learning process, and allows on this basis to predict, identify possible deviations, ways to prevent them, as well as adjust the learning process in order to improve quality training of qualified workers.

Pedagogical diagnostics acts as a process of establishing and studying the signs that characterize the state of various elements of the pedagogical system and the conditions of its functioning. This is necessary to predict possible development trends, deviations, prevent undesirable trends through pedagogical correction measures and stimulate positive elements of development (individuals, groups, pedagogical phenomena). Pedagogical diagnostics is carried out from the perspective of the subject of pedagogy as a science and aims to develop a pedagogical diagnosis and pedagogical corrective measures, while acting as a relatively independent branch of pedagogical knowledge, reflecting the theory and practice of pedagogical diagnostics and fulfilling the role of a service, auxiliary discipline in the structure of pedagogy. It is similar in its scientific status to pedagogical prognostics and pedagogical ethics. The components of the pedagogical process are objects of pedagogical diagnostics: these are the teacher, the student, the content, methods, means and results of pedagogical activity, as well as the patterns of the pedagogical process¹. The following functions of pedagogical diagnostics are distinguished². A feedback function that allows a teacher to manage the process of personality formation, controlling his actions with the help of information about the pedagogical process that makes it possible to focus on achieving the best option for a pedagogical solution. A function for assessing the effectiveness of teaching activities, based on comparison of achieved pedagogical results with criteria and indicators.

The function is educational and stimulating, taking into account that when diagnosing, the teacher needs not only to receive information about the students, but also to be involved in their activities, in the system of existing relationships. The functions are communicative and

constructive, based on the fact that interpersonal communication is impossible without knowledge and understanding of the partner. The implementation of these functions is possible provided that diagnostics determines the individual typological characteristics of students and the teacher in the process of their interaction. Functions of informing participants in the pedagogical process, i.e. reporting diagnostic results (if appropriate). The function is prognostic, implying the determination of the development prospects of the diagnosed object. Pedagogical diagnostics can be presented in several directions¹: • socio-pedagogical diagnostics, socio-pedagogical conditions and factors that actively influence the pedagogical process (social macro- and microenvironment, family, out-of-school institutions, etc.); • organizational and methodological diagnostics, methodological, organizational, material and technical conditions and the possibility of realizing the goals and objectives of the pedagogical process; • diagnostics of good manners, manifestations of good manners of students in consciousness and behavior and tendencies of good manners; • didactic diagnostics, educational achievements, training and learning ability of students. There are several options for determining the stages of diagnosis. The first was proposed by M.I. Shilova: the process of pedagogical diagnostics is associated with the collection, storage, processing of information and its use to manage the educational process. According to the second option (A.S. Belkin), at the first stage the function of recognizing an object by characteristic features is carried out, i.e., the process of primary accumulation of information occurs (observation, recording, memorizing everything that is connected with the life and activities of students), and the second stage involves processing information, recognizing the essence of the phenomenon being studied, and correlating the obtained data with practical activities.

The third option for constructing a diagnostic structure (L.N. Davydova) is based on the second and, taking into account the stages identified in the general theory of diagnostics, adds a number of specific stages: • determining the object, goals and objectives of pedagogical diagnostics; • putting forward a hypothesis and its subsequent testing, planning the process of the upcoming diagnosis; • selection of diagnostic tools (criteria, levels, methods); • collection of information about the object (correlation of the real state of the object with the normative-optimal one); • processing of received information (analysis, systematization and classification); • synthesis of the components of the diagnosed object into some new unity based on the analysis of reliable information; • forecasting the prospects for the further development of the diagnosed object, justification and assessment of the pedagogical diagnosis; • practical application of pedagogical diagnosis, correction of the management of the pedagogical process in order to transform the diagnosed object. In highlighting the stages of diagnosis, the author of the fourth version (T.V. Kupriyanchik) also relies on the stages defined in the general theory of diagnosis and adds new ones, characteristic specifically for pedagogical diagnostics: identification of internal and external conditions that determine one or another level of personality development; determination of the zone of proximal development; thinking about the necessary pedagogical measures for further development and personality formation.

Thus, an analysis of the literature on the problem allows us to conclude that pedagogical diagnostics is based on the logic of identifying stages defined in the general theory of diagnostics, but at the same time identifies a number of its own specific stages. Based on the above, we can conclude that pedagogical diagnostics is a specific type of diagnostics, since it has a specific object of diagnosis and a unique approach to its study; is an independent component of pedagogical

activity, present at all its stages; characterized by the presence of functions and principles that are different from other types of diagnostics; has a special structure and a number of specific stages.

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